

THE CHINESE MODEL FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Facing the new background of re-examining China's development path and deepening reform of systems and mechanisms, it is necessary to re-interpret the Chinese model from the perspective of sustainable development. This article briefly analyzes the advantages and characteristics of the Chinese model from the perspective of sustainable development, and proposes how to establish and improve a comprehensive sustainable development decision-making mechanism with Chinese characteristics. Then, based on the current national conditions, suggestions are made on the innovation and improvement of the internal systems and mechanisms of the Chinese model from the perspective of sustainable development.

Keywords: sustainable development, Chinese model, development perspective.

Introduction

The report of the 20th CPC National Congress profoundly expounded that Chinese-style modernization is modernization of harmonious coexistence between man and nature, made major arrangements and deployments for promoting green development and harmonious coexistence between man and nature, and pointed out the direction for advancing the construction of a beautiful China. The core of these important ideas is to achieve a balance between economic growth and environmental protection, to ensure long-term social development while maintaining ecological sustainability [1]. The Chinese model includes a series of development concepts and a series of systems and mechanisms that are conducive to economic and social development based on China's national conditions. However,

it is by no means a solidified development model. Instead, it is guided by the socialist political system with Chinese characteristics with the Communist Party of China as the core and the socialist theoretical system with Marxism as the guide. It starts from the pattern of economic development changes at home and abroad, and constantly refines and innovates the development mode and path of socialism with Chinese characteristics in the process of building contemporary socialism with Chinese characteristics, forming a Chinese localized sustainable development model that integrates the socialist system with Chinese characteristics, the socialist system, the socialist development theory, and the socialist sustainable development path. China's sustainable sustainable development actions from 1986 to 2020 are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Sustained sustainable development actions of China from 1986 to 2020 [11]

1. The quality and characteristics of the Chinese model from the perspective of sustainable development

First, the unity of growth, innovation and adherence to the socialist system. Compared with relatively mature development models, the primary feature of the Chinese model is growth. On the whole, the Chinese model has not yet been finalized and is constantly adapting to the changes in contemporary Chinese national conditions, the global economic and political situation, that is, it is constantly being revised, adjusted and transformed, and continuously innovating. Since the international financial crisis in 2008, China has placed more emphasis on the comprehensive development of the economy and society, transforming from low-end industries to high-end industries and green industries; it has placed more emphasis on innovation so that the Chinese model can remain vibrant [2]. At the same time, the foundation of the Chinese model is to creatively adhere to and develop the basic socialist economic system, so the growth of the Chinese model is inseparable from adhering to the socialist system, because the superiority of the socialist system with Chinese characteristics has been fully demonstrated and is becoming increasingly obvious. In this regard, Xi Jinping firmly pointed out that the road determines the destiny, and it is not easy to find a correct road, and we must continue to move forward unswervingly.

Second, the unity of worldliness and localism. The growth of the Chinese model is a unique development pattern formed to adapt to the general situation and background of contemporary world economic and social development, such as the division of labor in the international community caused by globalization, the integration of economic and political systems, international cooperation and coordination of international relations, and the solution to the common survival and development problems faced by mankind, in order to solve China's own development. It is checked and balanced by China's national conditions and contemporary Chinese cultural ideology, and has certain path dependence and local characteristics. Therefore, American scholars believe that the Chinese model is an example of applying universality to particularity or transforming globality into locality. Moreover, this model is imitated not because it is a universal model, but because of its practice of combining universality with specific historical environment. We say that it is actually a feasible way of combining Marxist ideology, the fine style of the Communist Party of China and traditional Chinese thought and culture to innovatively solve the current problems of China's economic development and governance.

Third, the unity of independence and continuous absorption of positive factors from both inside and outside. In essence, the Chinese model is an independent and self-reliant development path that is explored and explored based on the actual national conditions of the country [3]. It does not blindly imitate or copy the development models of other countries, but actively draws on all the beneficial experiences and wisdom of the world's modernization development models, based on the practice of China's socialist construction, to develop a development mechanism that is compatible with China's social development. China's development

and modernization process has never been dependent on any external forces in the world. It is independently seeking its own development path under the premise of safeguarding the fundamental interests of the country and national security. However, China is by no means seeking self-development in isolation. Instead, in the context of opening up to the outside world, it actively integrates into the trend of global development, continuously exchanges and cooperates with the outside world in culture, technology, systems, economic entities, and economic resources, continuously absorbs new elements of advanced culture and advanced productivity, creates new systems, new mechanisms, and new operating rules that are conducive to China's own development, and seeks better and larger international cooperation and development space.

Fourth, the harmonious unity of fairness and efficiency. The sustainable development path of contemporary China adheres to the two value orientations of fairness and efficiency, and strives to achieve the harmonious unity of fairness and efficiency. The market economy can promote the continuous improvement of micro-efficiency, while the socialist economic system is conducive to promoting the stability of the macro-economy. In the process of development, emphasizing the construction of China's socialist harmonious society is conducive to promoting social fairness, promoting efficiency, and taking the path of common prosperity. Under the principle of fairness, the pursuit of the realization of the overall interests of all members of society is the goal. Among them, the pursuit of social fairness can strengthen the satisfaction of social members with the return of personal efforts, thereby mobilizing their enthusiasm for value creation, and then bringing about the rapid development of high efficiency in the whole society. And the rapid development of high efficiency can create good conditions and necessary social foundation for further realizing social fairness.

2. Establish and improve a comprehensive decision-making mechanism for sustainable development with Chinese characteristics

In 1994, the Chinese government took the lead in issuing the world's first national sustainable development program, the China Agenda 21, which clearly proposed to "gradually establish a comprehensive decision-making mechanism and coordination management mechanism to promote sustainable development" as the main goal and basic policy means for implementing China's major sustainable development strategy actions [4]. At present, although comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development has been reflected in China's national economic and social development plans, major economic and technological policies and development strategies, and major engineering construction; comprehensive decision-making is moving towards concretization, institutionalization, and legalization; some relatively developed coastal regions in China have carried out a series of important practical activities to establish and improve regional comprehensive decision-making mechanisms for sustainable development, but the comprehensive decision-making mechanism for sustainable development has not yet been truly established in China.

At present, the establishment and improvement of a comprehensive decision-making mechanism for sustainable development with Chinese characteristics should start from the following aspects:

1. Establish and improve the organizational system, leadership mechanism, coordination mechanism and incentive mechanism for comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development.

2. Establish and improve an evaluation system for comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development and establish the prerequisites for comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development.

3. Establish and improve the public participation mechanism for comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development, and comprehensive decision-making should follow the mass line.

4. To establish and improve administrative support measures for comprehensive decision-making on sustainable development, the top leaders of the Party and government should personally take charge and assume overall responsibility, and earnestly implement the administrative leadership environmental protection target responsibility system.

5. We must actively accept supervision from the National People's Congress, the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference and the news media on major decision-making matters related to sustainable development.

6. Establish and improve the information release system and hearing system for major decision-making processes in sustainable development, and strengthen publicity to create a social and cultural atmosphere for comprehensive decision-making in sustainable development.

2.1 Improving sustainable development with Chinese characteristics requires establishing and improving the "ecological transfer payment" system

The ecological transfer payment system is an important policy support means for developed countries such as the United States and Germany to implement ecological environmental protection. Drawing on the successful experience of these developed countries, establishing and improving my country's ecological transfer payment system is an important fiscal policy means for my country's ecological environmental protection and sustainable development capacity building. The construction of the ecological transfer payment system is one of the central links of my country's sustainable economic policy system.

At present, my country has launched some exploratory attempts for ecological environmental compensation in the protection, restoration and construction of the ecological environment. However, due to the imperfect mechanism, compensation cannot be carried out completely according to reason and law, and the departmental administrative color is strong, resulting in inadequate compensation. To this end, first of all, it is necessary to establish a multi-level ecological transfer payment system at the national, regional and river basin levels that is beneficial, reasonable, standardized and unified: first, developed regions have the need and obligation to increase financial and technical support for important ecological function areas in the central and

western regions across the country; second, downstream areas actively make necessary compensation to upstream ecological protection areas, which can be cross-provincial, or cross-city and county within the province; third, compensation between different industries, different ecological elements or natural resource development units in local areas. Secondly, the establishment and improvement of the ecological transfer payment system requires the following relationships to be handled well: first, the relationship between the east, middle and west or the upper, middle and lower reaches; second, the relationship between the short term and the long term or the relationship between the present and future generations; third, the relationship between market role and government action. Third, the establishment and improvement of the ecological transfer payment system should follow the following principles: first, whoever uses it should compensate; whoever benefits or whoever causes damage should pay; second, the principle of promoting the common development of the protected areas and the beneficiary areas; and the principle of combining meeting needs with practical feasibility [5].

We believe that, at present, the key tasks for establishing and improving the ecological transfer payment system are: 1. Strengthen legislative work and establish the ecological transfer payment system on the basis of legalization. 2. Establish an evaluation standard system for ecological transfer payments. 3. Use the form of "fiscal transfer payments" to increase the country's investment in western regions, especially in ethnic minority areas. 4. Use the form of "project support" to focus on the development of ecological immigrants and alternative industries in ecological and environmental protection areas. 5. It is recommended to levy a national ecological compensation tax; while strengthening the pollution discharge fee collection, gradually implement the fee-to-tax reform. 6. Actively explore the "hematopoietic" way to achieve ecological transfer payments [6].

2.2 Improving sustainable development with Chinese characteristics requires improving and implementing a sustainable development policy evaluation system

Since the 1980s, developed countries such as the United States and Germany have gradually developed and upgraded the "environmental assessment" of enterprises, major engineering projects, regions and river basins to the sustainability assessment of national environmental economic, social and other policies. Among them, the assessment of national environmental policies is also called "strategic environmental impact assessment". Since "strategic environmental impact assessment" is often carried out before the implementation of national policies, it plays a preventive function for national ecological and environmental protection. It is considered to be a system that prevents ecological and environmental damage from the source and is one of the most important pillars of preventive environmental policy [7]. After nearly 20 years of exploration, developed countries such as the United States and Japan finally focused the focus of sustainable policy assessment on improving policy quality, emphasizing that the

fundamental purpose of policy evaluation is to improve policy quality.

China's sustainable development policy assessment is mainly reflected in environmental impact assessment and environmental policy assessment. The earliest can be traced back to the "Environmental Protection Law (Trial)" formulated in 1979. My country's practice shows that policies, especially economic policies, have a significant impact on the ecological environment. The deterioration of my country's ecological environment is directly related to the implementation of improper economic policies. For example, in the "Decision of the State Council on the Main Points of Current Industrial Policy" in 1989, the industries listed as key national support industries include papermaking, electroplating, leather, printing and dyeing, and coking. Facts have proved that the rapid development of these industries in just a few years has caused inestimable environmental damage to China. On August 3, 1996, the State Council issued the "Decision on Several Issues Concerning Environmental Protection". Some enterprises that seriously polluted the environment were strictly ordered to be banned or closed within a time limit. In the following year, more than 65,000 small enterprises such as papermaking that seriously polluted the environment were banned or closed across the country, and the Agricultural Bank of China alone could not recover more than 5 billion yuan in loan principal and interest due to this action. If policy evaluation is carried out in advance, this problem can be prevented. [8]

Drawing on the basic experience of sustainable policy evaluation in developed countries, we suggest that we establish and improve the evaluation system and system of my country's sustainable development policy as soon as possible:

1. Establish an independent monitoring and evaluation agency. This agency will be responsible for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of national sustainable development policies and their impact.

2. Formulate policy evaluation guidelines as soon as possible to promote the standardization and regulation of policy evaluation.

3. Formulate national and regional sustainable development zoning, and implement zoning and classification assessments of sustainable development policies.

4. Establish an evaluation committee composed of experts from various parties.

5. Ensure that the evaluation results are reflected in the implementation of policies and give full play to the effectiveness of policy evaluation.

6. Establish a mechanism for public release and feedback of evaluation results.

3. Suggestions on innovation and improvement of the internal system and mechanism of the Chinese model from the perspective of sustainable development

At present, under the guidance of the Chinese Dream of realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, the internal system and mechanism framework of the Chinese model that is conducive to sustainable development has basically been formed, mainly including: the system and mechanism of the sustainable development model of the Chinese economy with Chinese characteristics at the economic level, the system and mechanism of socialist democracy with Chinese characteristics at the political level, the system and mechanism of a harmonious society with Chinese characteristics at the social level, the system and mechanism of culture under the guidance of the theoretical system of socialism with Chinese characteristics at the cultural and ideological level, the system and mechanism of ecological security with harmony between man and nature at the natural level, and the system and mechanism of peaceful coexistence and harmony between China and the world at the external level. Of course, we must be soberly aware that the system and mechanism and its operating rules in the Chinese model that currently supports China's sustainable development still have many aspects that are not adapted to or even hinder sustainable development, and must be continuously reformed, innovated and improved, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Production-living-ecological space framework for sustainable development based on land-use type. [12]

3.1 Suggestions on innovation and improvement of the socialist economic development system and mechanism with Chinese characteristics under the perspective of sustainable development

The focus of innovation is: first, to continuously strengthen the basic socialist economic system, that is, the distribution mode in which multiple ownership systems coexist with public ownership as the main body and multiple factors participate in distribution with distribution according to work as the main body. This is one of the basic conditions. At present, the key thing to do is to actively promote the rapid development of the mixed-ownership economy and actively innovate and improve the socialist distribution system with Chinese characteristics that integrates fairness and efficiency. Second, to realize a system and mechanism that is conducive to independent innovation. This is also one of the basic conditions [9]. The external guarantee for the formation of the independent innovation system and mechanism is to create a fair competition environment for market economic entities and provide the fundamental conditions for innovation to become a competitive force for market economic entities. At the same time, government departments at all levels must establish and improve a policy support system that stimulates various market entities to carry out independent innovation, drive independent innovation with policy innovation, make innovation a habit, and make entrepreneurship a way of life. Third, to realize the innovation and improvement of the comprehensive system around the operation of the market economy. In other words, let the economic resources that should be allocated by the market return to the market allocation standard completely, and continuously reduce the intervention, control and monopoly of government departments in the allocation of various economic resources. Fourth, we will achieve innovation and improvement in

systems and mechanisms that are conducive to foreign economic development and international economic cooperation, and guide and promote more Chinese companies and capital to go global.

3.2 Suggestions on Socialist Democracy with Chinese Characteristics from the Perspective of Sustainable Development

At present, the innovation and improvement of the governance system and mechanism must be carried out around improving the modernization level of the national governance system and governance capacity. The political system reform must not stop, and it must not be based on the Western democratic system as a reference model. It is necessary to innovate and improve the socialist democratic political system with Chinese characteristics in light of China's national conditions. First, it is to strengthen the core leadership system and mechanism of the Communist Party of China as the ruling party, as well as the improvement of the system and mechanism in which the people are the masters of the country, the government exercises power in accordance with regulations, and the government exercises power effectively. Second, it is to give full play to the core function of the people's congress, the fundamental political system, in the operation of political power, and promote the enrichment and normalization of the functions of the grassroots people's congress as a national power organ. Third, it is to promote the diversification and enrichment of democratic consultation, a unique form of democratic political system in China. Fourth, the key to reforming and improving the mechanism for the reasonable exercise of power is to establish and improve the power operation mechanism framework in which decision-making power, executive power and supervisory power are mutually restricted and complementary[10]. Fifth, deepen administrative system reform and focus on resolving the relationship

between government management and services. All that should be managed by the government must be managed in place and well; all that should be delegated must be delegated; all that should transform government functions must be transformed as soon as possible, so as to improve the government's service and governance functions for economic and social development.

3.3 Suggestions for innovation and improvement of the operating system and mechanism of a harmonious society in China from the perspective of sustainable development

First, reform the income distribution system, gradually improve the situation of excessive social income gap, and build a distribution system and operation mechanism to achieve common prosperity and continuously improve the living standards of urban and rural residents. It is imperative to establish and improve the policy system for regulating primary distribution and property income distribution, and it is the top priority to protect the middle and low-income groups, especially to narrow the income gap between urban and rural areas and continuously increase the income of rural residents. Second, gradually establish and improve the lifelong education system for all people, build a learning society support system, continuously improve the basic quality, moral cultivation, and professional skills of each socialist builder, and continuously inject internal motivation into the construction of a socialist harmonious society. Third, establish a stable employment support system and a universal social security system. Fourth, establish and improve a comprehensive social security prevention and control early warning system and a comprehensive national security (including territory and sovereignty, economy, politics, culture, sustainable development potential, etc.) guarantee system. Fifth, improve the social security system.

3.4 Suggestions on the great development and prosperity of cultural industries and cultural undertakings under the guidance of the theoretical system of socialism with Chinese characteristics in the context of sustainable development

Comprehensively promoting the progress and development of cultural industries and cultural undertakings is to build a contemporary socialist cultural system with Chinese characteristics from the height of realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, organically integrate the inheritance of China's multi-ethnic excellent traditional culture, the internalization of socialist culture, and the introduction of the world's latest era culture, and strive to construct a new socialist cultural system with national cohesion, internal innovation, and external tolerance. Second, it is necessary to strengthen the whole society's recognition of the socialist cultural system with Chinese characteristics in a

wider range of fields and adopt more effective methods, continuously inject modern social culture and ecological civilization construction awareness into cultural development practice, create a new concept of sustainable development of socialist culture, and guide and shape the new cultural system of contemporary China on this basis. Third, it is necessary to build a prosperous and developed socialist cultural system and mechanism with Chinese characteristics. The core point is to pay attention to the improvement and internalization of the economic, social, and family moral qualities of the whole people, promote the great development and prosperity of positive and upward literary and entertainment undertakings and industries that are beneficial to the physical and mental health of the masses, and inherit and carry forward the excellent traditional national culture.

3.5 Suggestions for innovation and improvement of the system and mechanism for harmony between man and nature under the perspective of sustainable development

The establishment of a harmonious system and mechanism between man and nature is mainly through strengthening the construction of socialist ecological civilization and guiding and encouraging economic entities to consciously protect and improve the natural ecological environment with policies. First, economic entities are constrained by law to adjust their behaviors that may damage the natural ecological environment so that they act within the scope permitted by the legal system. At the same time, environmental damage, resource consumption and ecological benefits are included in the evaluation system of economic and social development, and the weight of various indicators reflecting the construction of ecological civilization in the government performance assessment is increased. Second, the incentive and constraint mechanism of green production, green circulation and green consumption is innovated and improved, and a more transparent feedback mechanism for the impact of production, circulation and consumption on the natural ecology is formed, so as to promote the optimization of traditional industrial chains and make modern green industries the goal consciously pursued by all kinds of producers. Third, the natural ecological security early warning mechanism is innovated and improved. For the geographical space of natural ecological environment early warning, measures to slow down or stop redevelopment should be taken according to specific circumstances, and a sound natural ecological environment compensation mechanism should be established to carry out timely, appropriate and more intensive natural ecological restoration and repair, as shown in Figure 3.

The driving mechanism of sustainable development change at county level in China within production-living-ecological space framework.

Fig. 3. Flow diagram illustrating modeling process for the driving mechanism of sustainable development change. [12]

3.6 Suggestions for innovation and improvement of the external relations mediation mechanism based on equality, mutual benefit, harmonious coexistence and common development under the perspective of sustainable development

China's development is an important part of the world's development. Therefore, China's development must seek and develop a new type of foreign relations of harmonious coexistence, equality, mutual benefit and common development under the premise of resolutely defending national sovereignty, territorial security and national core interests. First, we should focus on seeking to establish a cooperative mechanism for regional common security. Under this mechanism framework, we should not seek to dominate or control regional common security, but actively promote and realize regional cooperative security mechanisms to create a good peaceful environment for China's sustainable development. Second, we should focus on adjusting foreign economic relations and strategic goals, and use the "Belt and Road" strategy to create a new situation for foreign economic exchanges. Under the guidance of the "Belt and Road" strategy, we should strengthen regional economic cooperation among relevant countries, actively promote the superimposed development of multiple bilateral partnerships, and use their respective advantages from the central to the local level to include more countries and regions and develop in depth. Third, we should further promote trade liberalization. Under the premise of moderately protecting the security of domestic weak industries and important strategic resources, import and export goods and services should be arranged more by the market, rapidly improve the competitiveness and brand awareness of China's export goods, and build a new framework for sustainable development of foreign trade that is compatible with the world's largest import and export trade country in conclusion

As environmental protection has become the focus of global attention, China's sustainable development mechanism is particularly important. At present, the Chinese model has the quality and inherent characteristics of sustainable development, which are mainly manifested in the unity of growth, innovation and adherence to the socialist system, the unity of worldliness and localism, the unity of independence and continuous absorption of positive factors from both inside and outside, the harmonious unity of fairness and efficiency, the unity of integrity and comprehensiveness, and the unity of the leadership of the Party and the people being the masters of the country. In the face of many factors and conditions that restrict and hinder the sustainable development of the Chinese model under the existing system and mechanism, we still need to continuously improve and innovate the internal system and mechanism of the Chinese model. This is of great significance to promoting China's sustainable development.

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